

THE NUMBER AND LOCATION OF EIGENVALUES OF THE TWO PARTICLE DISCRETE SCHRODINGER OPERATORS

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Let $\mathbb{T} = [-\pi, \pi]$ be the one - dimensional torus. Let $L^2(\mathbb{T})$ be the Hilbert space of squareintegrable functions on $\mathbb{T}$. $L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T}) \in L^2(\mathbb{T})$ is the Hilbert space of square-integrable even functions on $\mathbb{T}$. For any $\mu; \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and $k \in \mathbb{T}$ the Schrodinger operator $H_{\mu\lambda}(k)$ is bounded and self-adjoint acting in $L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T})$ as

$$H_{\mu\lambda}(k) = H_0(k) + V_{\mu\lambda}$$

Here the non-perturbed operator $H_0(k)$, $k \in \mathbb{T}$ is the multiplication operator by the function $E_k(\cdot)$ acting in $L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T})$ as

$$(H_0(k)f)(p) = \varepsilon_k(p) f(p), \quad \varepsilon_k(p) = 2[1 - \cos\frac{k}{2} \cos p], \quad p \in \mathbb{T}.$$

The perturbation operator $V_{\mu\lambda}$ is defined as

$$(V_{\mu\lambda}f)(p) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{T}} (\mu + \lambda \cos p \cdot \cos t) f(t) dt, \quad f \in L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T}).$$

The operator $H_0(k)$, $k \in \mathbb{T}$ is the operator of multiplication by a continuous real function $E_k(p)$ defined in $\mathbb{T}$, therefore its spectrum consist of the essential spectrum:

$$\sigma(H_0(k)) = \sigma_{ess}(H_0(k)) = [\varepsilon_{min}(k), \varepsilon_{max}(k)],$$

with

$$\varepsilon_{min}(k) := \min_{q \in \mathbb{T}} \varepsilon_k(q) = 2(1 - \cos\frac{k}{2}) \geq 0,$$

$$\varepsilon_{max}(k) := \max_{q \in \mathbb{T}} \varepsilon_k(q) = 2(1 + \cos\frac{k}{2}) \leq 4.$$

The perturbation $V_{\mu\lambda}$ is an operator of rank-two. Hence, from the Weyl theorem [5] the essential spectrum of $H_{\mu\lambda}(k)$ coincides with the spectrum of $H_0(k)$, i.e.,

$$\sigma_{ess}(H_{\mu\lambda}(k)) = \sigma(H_0(k)).$$

We define the Birman-Schwinger operator in $L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T})$ as

$$(B_{\mu\lambda}(k, z)) = -V_{\mu\lambda}R_0(k, z), \quad z \in \mathbb{C} \setminus [\varepsilon_{min}(k), \varepsilon_{max}(k)].$$

For any fixed values of the parameters $\mu, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, the determinant of the operator $H_{\mu\lambda}(k) - zI$ is understood as the Fredholm determinant of the operator

$$I - B_{\mu\lambda}(k, z),$$

$$\Delta(\mu, \lambda, k, z) := \det(I - B_{\mu\lambda}(k, z)) = \det (H_{\mu\lambda}(k) - zI).$$

In the case $k \neq \pi$ the determinant $\Delta(\mu, \lambda, k, z)$ of $H_{\mu\lambda}(k)$ can be represented as $\Delta(\mu, \lambda, k, z) = (1 + \mu a(k, z))(1 + \lambda a(k, z)) - \mu\lambda b^2(k, z)$, where

$$a(k, z) := \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{T}} \frac{dt}{\varepsilon_k(t) - z}$$

$$b(k, z) := \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{T}} \frac{\cos dt}{\varepsilon_k(t) - z}$$

$$c(k, z) := \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{T}} \frac{\cos^2 a dt}{\varepsilon_k(t) - z}.$$

We define the asymptotics

$$C_{\frac{-1}{2}}^-(\mu, \lambda, k) = -\mu\lambda - 2\lambda\cos\frac{k}{2} - 4\mu\cos\frac{k}{2}$$

and

$$C_{\frac{-1}{2}}^+(\mu, \lambda, k) = \mu\lambda - 2\lambda\cos\frac{k}{2} - 4\mu\cos\frac{k}{2}.$$

of the function $\Delta(\mu, \lambda, k, z)$ at $\varepsilon_{min}(k)$, the bottom and at $\varepsilon_{max}(k)$, the top of the essential spectrum of $H_{\mu\lambda}(k)$.

We define a partition of the μ - λ plane of parameters $\mu, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ $\mathbb{G}_{\alpha\beta}$ to some connected components $\mathbb{G}_{\alpha\beta}(k)$, $\alpha, \beta = 0, 1, 2$, by means of the curves (hyperbola) $\Gamma_1^-(k)$, $\Gamma_2^-(k)$ and $\Gamma_1^+(k)$, $\Gamma_2^+(k)$ which are zeros of $C_{\frac{-1}{2}}^-(\mu, \lambda, k)$ and $C_{\frac{-1}{2}}^+(\mu, \lambda, k)$.

Theorem 1. Let $k \in \mathbb{T}$, $k \neq \pi$ be fixed.

1. For any $(\mu, \lambda) \in \mathbb{G}_{20}(k)$ the operator $H_{\lambda\mu}(k)$ has exactly two eigenvalues $z_1(\mu; \lambda; k)$ and $z_2(\mu; \lambda; k)$ in $(-\infty; \varepsilon_{min}(k))$.
2. For any $(\mu, \lambda) \in \mathbb{G}_{10}(k)$ the operator $H_{\lambda\mu}(k)$ has a unique eigenvalue $z_1(\mu; \lambda; k)$, which lies in $(-\infty; \varepsilon_{min}(k))$.
3. For any $(\mu, \lambda) \in \mathbb{G}_{11}(k)$ the operator $H_{\lambda\mu}(k)$ has two eigenvalues satisfying $z_1(\mu; \lambda; k) < \varepsilon_{min}(k)$ and $z_2(\mu; \lambda; k) > \varepsilon_{max}(k)$.
4. For any $(\mu, \lambda) \in \mathbb{G}_{01}(k)$ the operator $H_{\lambda\mu}(k)$ has a unique eigenvalue $z_1(\mu; \lambda; k)$ which lies in $(\varepsilon_{max}(k); +\infty)$.
5. For any $(\mu, \lambda) \in \mathbb{G}_{02}(k)$ the operator $H_{\lambda\mu}(k)$ has two eigenvalues $z_1(\mu; \lambda; k)$ and $z_2(\mu; \lambda; k)$ in $(\varepsilon_{max}(k); +\infty)$.

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